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The Impact of Population Dynamics on Growth and Expansion of Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Population dynamics changes in the size, structure, and spatial distribution of human populations remain one of the most important drivers of urban transformation across Sub-Saharan Africa. As urban centres continue to expand, demographic pressure intensifies demand for land, housing, infrastructure, and environmental resources. Sokoto Metropolis, one of northwestern Nigeria's fastest growing cities, has experienced rapid population growth over the last six decades, driven by high fertility rates, declining mortality, and increasing rural-urban migration, particularly due to insecurity in neighbouring local government areas. This study examines the impact of population dynamics on the growth, land-use transition, and spatial expansion of Sokoto Metropolis from 1960 to 2022. A mixed-method approach was adopted involving demographic data analysis, geospatial mapping of land use/land cover changes, and field surveys to assess infrastructure stress and environmental implications. Findings indicate that built-up areas expanded from 26.3 km² in 1986 to more than 80 km² by 2020, representing over 200% spatial growth within three decades. Population increased from approximately 50,000 in 1960 to over 685,000 in 2022. This growth has exerted significant pressure on basic infrastructure housing, water supply, health care, sanitation, education, electricity, transportation resulting in environmental degradation, loss of agricultural land, and proliferation of informal settlements. The study concludes that unmanaged population growth threatens urban sustainability and recommends integrated planning, improved demographic monitoring, strengthened infrastructure investment, and sustainable land-use policies to enhance the resilience of Sokoto Metropolis.

Keywords: Population Dynamics, Urban Growth, Infrastructure, Sokoto Metropolis, Urban Expansion

INTRODUCTION

Population embraces the sum of total human resources available in a given country (Akin-Tunde, 2013). The important aspects of population include its population size, spatial distribution, structure or age, sex, composition, growth rate, birth rate and death rate, standard of living, health and educational status. But, population dynamics focuses on the change in size, demographic structure and spatial distribution of a population over time (UNDFPA, 2013). Such changes can be traced to changes in natural, environmental, economic, political circumstances, reproductive health management technology, and changes in human reproductive and location decisions (UNDESA/UNDFPA, 2013; ACF/IRIS, 2016).

In the same vein, the UNFPA, (2012) explains that population dynamics deals with the size and age composition of populations as dynamical systems, and the biological and environmental processes driving them (such as birth and death rates), and by immigration and emigration. Example of such scenarios are ageing populations, population growth or population decline. The main observable characteristics of population dynamics are size, density, dispersion, sex distribution and age

The birth rate of a population describes the number of new individuals produced in that population per unit time while the death rate describes the number of individuals who die in population. The immigration rate is the number of individuals who move into population from different area per unit time. The emigration rates describe the number of individuals who migrate out from a unit area at a particular time.

Based on the current rate of population growth, the global population of 8 billion is expected to reach 8.6 billion by 2030 (UNDESA, 2015). The world population growth will be concentrated in countries like India, Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo, Pakistan, Ethiopia, Tanzania, United States of America, Uganda and Indonesia by 2050 (UN 2015). It is noteworthy to state that the world is faced with unprecedented diversity in demographic situation across countries and regions, as well as within the countries. Such diversity is mostly found in evolving demographic structure and changing proportion of youth and elderly groups, and different rates of fertility, morbidity and mortality, population growth, urbanization and internal and international migration (UN 2015).

Population growth is now more prominent in urban areas of the world. This made experts to conclude that the world is fast becoming urbanized (UN, 2015) and something drastic needs to be done to make urban areas sustainable. It is argued that more than 4 billion people out of the 7.3 billion are now living in cities. This figure is expected to rise to 60% by the year 2030 (Revi, 2017). The fact that close to two-thirds of the global economy emanates from cities and this is expected to rise to three-fourths by 2030 made cities to continue to attract people and investments (Revi, 2017). There are currently over 33 megacities in the world as at the year 2022 and the figure is expected to rise to 51 by 2050. These are cities with more than 10 million population (UN, 2018).

With the largest and one of the most rapidly growing cities in sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria has experienced the phenomenon of urbanization as thoroughly as any African nation, but its experience has also been unique--in scale, in pervasiveness, and in historical antecedents. The explosion of urban population in Nigeria, has not been matched by a corresponding change in economic, technological and social development. This could be attributed to economic stagnation and decline in the growth of industries.

In recent times, population growth has been so prominent in the developing countries of the world and Nigeria has witnessed unprecedented population growth over the years. The population census for Nigeria in the year 1962 revealed a figure of 47,029,818 million. This rises to 88,994,211 million and 140,433,796 million based on the 1991 and 2006 censuses respectively (NPC, 1991 and 2007) and the current projection placed the population of Nigeria to be around 216,435,521 million (UN World Urbanization Prospect, 2022) and it is expected to reach about 401 million by the year 2050. Going by this figure, it is obvious that the population of Nigeria has more than quadrupled since independence. The growth has been accompanied by the emergence of new urban areas and the growth of existing ones in Nigeria. For instance, there are less than ten urban areas in Nigeria as of 1904 but the current figure has put urban areas in Nigeria at more than 700 with about 40 urban areas having a population of more than half a million (500,000) and seven cities with over one million population (Ayeni, 1978). Akin to the global population changes, Sokoto Urban is undergoing massive urbanization due to population growth, redistribution of activities and expansion of the built environment accompanied by both positive and negative consequences. Recent study conducted by United Nations (2022) indicated that population of Sokoto urban was about 641,000 in 2020, with a significant increase of 3.5%, while in 2021 it was 662,000, a significant increase of 3.28% and also in 2022 the population of the urban was over 685,000 a significant increase of 3.47% (U.N 2022). It is based on this premise, this study seeks to examine population dynamics and how it impacted on the growth and expansion of Sokoto urban over the years.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research design is the set of procedures used in collecting and analyzing measure of variable in a specific research problem (Kirumbi,2018). It represents the major methodological work of the study being the distinctive and specific approach which is best suited to answer the research questions. Therefore, this research employed a mixed approach. The reason for employing both

approaches is to enable adequate and flexible pattern that allows accommodation of various social findings. The study adopted descriptive survey design which enable this research gathered data from sample population. The mixed approach drawing on primary data collected through structured questionnaire administered across 27 selected wards, as well as interviews with relevant stakeholders from ministry of environment, Urban and Regional Planning Board, Ministry of land, housing and country planning, ministry of water resources, National bureau of statistics and Independent National Electoral Commission. Secondary data was sourced from journals, official documents, text books, Internet, and Google. However, systematic sampling techniques was employed with samples size of 399 household using Yamane's Formula. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as percentage, bar graph, pie chart and line graph and also geospatial was conducted through (land stat) Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) to determine the growth and expansion of Sokoto Metropolis.

Study Area

Sokoto urban lies between latitude 12° 55' and 13° 10'N and longitude 5° 09' and 5° 17'E. Sokoto Urban covers 16km radius from Giginya memorial stadium Sokoto. The urban covers the entire land of Sokoto South and Sokoto North local governments as well as western part of Dange –Shuni local government; (such as Kwannawa, Kosai, Giginya Barrack, Dambuwa, Sabaru) and Wamakko to the eastern part especially in areas around Guiwa, Bado, Arkilla, Gidan Fulani and Kalambaina, and also some part of Kware local government in areas like Moreh, Kurfi and Ruggar Liman. The instrument to be use in this research include questionnaire and interview. The questionnaire will solicit demographic information such as age group, occupation as well as information on the impact of population dynamics on the growth and expansion of Sokoto Urban. On the other hand, Key Informant Interview (KII) will be used for data collection from relevant government officials, agencies and parastatals. These agencies include, National Population Commission, National Bureau of Statistics, Sokoto Urban and Regional Planning Board, State Ministry of Land and Housing.

Figure1: Location of Sokoto Urban in Nigeria

Data Analysis

Data analysis will be presented objective by objective as follows:

This work

- Objective ii:** Determine the demographic characteristics of the population. This objective will also be analysed using descriptive statistics in the form of tables and charts.
- Objective iii:** Determine the extent of the growth and expansion of the urban. Change detection technique tool in ArcGIS will be used to determine the changes in the size of the built environment in the study area.
- Objective iv:** Find out the implication of population dynamics on provision of basic infrastructure in the area of study. Inventory method will be adopted in this regard. Attempt will be made to determine the adequacy or inadequacy of basic infrastructure in the study area.
- Objective v:** Determine the consequences of population growth on the environment. Descriptive statistics will also be used here.

Results

Addressing the Trend of Urban Growth in the Study Area

The analysis of information obtained from Landsat imageries for the period from 2000–2025. As stated under the methods section this study seeks to identify land cover changes as a result of trend of urban growth in the study area.

Table1: Trend of Urban Growth in Sokoto Metropolis (2000–2024) Based on NDBI Analysis

CLASS	NDBI 2000	NDBI 2005	NDBI 2010	NDBI 2015	NDBI 2020	NDBI 2024	Magnitude change (2000-2024)	Percentage Change (2000-2024)
BUILTUP	4791.98	67143	7627.6	8747.4	9587.7	11423	6631.02	138.40%
NON URNAN	23453	21518	20586	19506	18636	16785	-6668	-28.40%
WATER BODY	230.02	242.7	261.4	218.6	251.3	267	36.98	16.10%

Source: Authors NDBI Analysis, 2025

Figure 1: NDBI of the Study Area
Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

Figure 2: NDBI of the Study Area
Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

Figure 5: NDBI of the Study Area
Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

Figure 6: NDBI of the Study Area
Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

Figure 7: Trend of Built-Up Area Expansion (2000-2024)
Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

Figure 8: Land cover change Trends (2000-2024)

Source: Authors GIS Analysis 2025

The analysis of urban growth trends in Sokoto Metropolis from 2000 to 2024 reveals a significant expansion of built-up areas alongside a decline in non-urban land. The built-up area increased from **4,791.98 sq. km in 2000** to **11,423 sq. km in 2024**, marking a **138.4% rise**, indicating rapid urbanization. Conversely, non-urban areas decreased by **28.4%**, reflecting land conversion due to urban expansion. Water bodies experienced minor fluctuations but showed an overall increase of **16.1%**, possibly due to improved water management or seasonal variations. The findings suggest accelerated urban growth, particularly after 2010, likely driven by population increase, economic activities, and infrastructure development. If not properly managed, this trend may lead to urban congestion, environmental degradation, and inadequate infrastructure. Therefore, strict compliance with physical planning regulations is necessary to ensure sustainable urban development and efficient land use management in the study area.

Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

This section provides the demographic and social characteristics of the respondents in the study area. It comprised of ethnic characteristics, gender age composition, level of education, marital status, number of wives, household size, occupation, and average income of the respondents.

Table 2: Ethnic Group of the Respondents

Ethnic Group	Frequency	Percent (%)
Hausa	163	42.7
Fulani	91	23.8
Yoruba	59	15.4
Igbo	42	11.0
Others	27	7.1
Total	382	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 present the ethnic groups of the respondents in the study area. The analysis of the findings shows that the majority (163) of the respondents are Hausa and they constitute 42.7%. This was followed by Fulani that constitute 23.8%, Yoruba 15.4% and igbo also constitute 7.1% of the respondents. The dominance of Hausa ethnic group had confirmed that they are indigenous group in the and the early occupants of

Sokoto Urban. The finding also reveal the diversity of ethnic groups in the Urban which shaded light based on knowledge and experience on the population dynamics and urban of Sokoto Urban.

Changes in Physical growth and expansion of the urban from 2000 to 2024

In this section, Geographical information system was used to determine the changes in the physical growth and expansion of the Sokoto urban from year 2000 to 2024. The Normalized Difference Built up Index (NDBI) was used to detect these changes and expansion of the urban over years with an imagery of the city captured from 2000 to 2024 which indicated the built-up areas, non-built up areas and water body over the years.

Table 3 Normalized Difference Built of Index Results and percentage over years.

Urban Built-up Area	NDBI 2000	NDBI 2005	NDBI 2010	NDBI 2015	NDBI 2020	NDBI 2024	Magnitude Change (2000-2024)	Percentage change (2000-2024)
Built-up	4791.98	6714.3	7627.6	8747.4	9587.7	11423	6631.02	138.40%
Non-Urban	23453	21518	20586	19506	18636	16785	-6668	-28.40%
Water Body	230.02	242.7	261.4	218.6	251.3	267	36.98	16.10%
Total	28,475 hectares	28,475 hectares						

Table 3 present multi temporal analysis of Sokoto urban over years.The table shows Normalized Difference Built up Index (NDBI) of 2000,2005,2010 ,2015,2020, and 2024.The table also portray the percentage changes and the magnitudes change over the years and was done in hectares to determine the extent physical growth of the urban.

Population Dynamics and Growth

This section provides analysis of the results on population dynamics and growth in the study area.It indicated duration of stay of the respondents, determinant of population,factors that necessitate to change residence by respondents, description of the present destination (new settlement), factors of population dynamics in the study area, basic infrastructure in the study area,land use pattern in-the urban, and factors that attract population concentration in the newly formed areas of the Urban.

Table 4: Duration of Stay at present destination of the Respondents

Duration of residence	Frequency	Percent (%)
Less than 5 years	168	44.0
6-10 years	32	8.4
11-15 years	114	29.8
16-20 years	20	5.2
21 years above	48	12.6
Total	382	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 4 presents the duration of stay at present destination of the respondents in the study area.The analysis of the findings shows that, majority (168) of the respondents that constitutes (44%) have lived for less than 5 years. indicating influx of new residents and migrating in search of better economic opportunities, education and improved living conditions in the study area. However, respondents who lived for 11-15 years constitute 29.8 %. Those that stayed for 21 years and above are

48 respondents that constitutes (12.6%). Whereas the least are those who lived 16-20 years 5.2% However this category indicates respondents with longest duration of stay in the study area.

Figure 10: Determinant of population in the study area.

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Figure 10 presents the determinant of population in the study area. The results analysis shows that, birth rate is the major determinant of population dynamics in the area and constitutes 58%. This followed by number of immigrants population that constitutes 23.3%. Another significant determinant of population is death rate which constitutes 12.3% while least determinant are others with 6.5%. The finding reveals majority of the respondents highlight birth rate and immigrants are the major determinant of population growth in the Urban which reflects better health services and opportunities in the study area.

Table 5: Factors affecting population dynamics in the study area

Factors	Frequency	Percent (%)
form of marriage	171	44.8
Commercial activities	67	17.5
High Migration rate	48	12.6
Available of educational services	68	17.8
Government policies	28	7.3
Total	382	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 5 presents factors affecting population dynamics in the study area. The analysis of the results shows that, high birth rate or fertility due to culture and religious beliefs of marriage more than one wife can lead to high birth rate which account 44.8%. Followed by Available of educational services is another factor of population dynamics in the study area which constitute 17.8%. Another factor is commercial activities such as trading, and telecommunications (17.5%) while the high migration rate are also factor of population changes and constitute 12.6%. However, Government policies (7.3%) which can directly influence population dynamics such as family Planning constitutes 7.3%. The finding reveal prevalence of birth rate and educational services due cultural beliefs and religious beliefs and also level of education among women regard birth which can change the structure and composition of population in the Sokoto Urban.

Figure 11: Consequences of Population growth on housing infrastructure .
Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Figure 11 presents the specific consequences of population dynamics in study area. The analysis of the findings reveal significant challenges faced by the community. The most prominent consequence identified is the "high cost of land," and constitute 37% of responses. This reflecting the escalating prices of land in the Urban which a piece of land 50 by 50 are selling around 2-3 millions which is very difficult to afford. However, Overcrowding constitute 21% of responses, indicating that as the population increases, many areas are becoming densely populated. This can lead to numerous problems, including strain on infrastructure and reduced quality of life. Another specific consequence is "environmental degradation," reported by 23% of the respondents. This suggests that the pressures of population growth are contributing to environmental challenges, such as pollution, loss of green spaces, and unsustainable land use practices. Lastly, "increasing housing demands "constitute only 19% of respondents, emphasizing the need for more housing options as the population continues to grow. The finding was in line with Wesley and Peterson 2017 cited the rapid population growth and urbanization has been fuelled by massive influx of people from surrounding hinterland for jobs opportunities in various commercial enterprises which has made land value change. Also population growth had led to issue of poor housing quality because of the rush by some owners to change the land use pattern for quick profit which providing sub-standard building in the society.

Impact of population growth on the environment

This section provides insight analysis on the impact of population growth in the environment, and it also explore more views on the respondents regarding the implications of population growth in the environment such as; increase waste accumulation, frequent flooding and erosions, pollution and extinction of species.

Table 6: implication of population growth on the environment

Implications	Frequency	Percent (%)
Increase waste accumulation	147	38.5
Frequent flooding and erosion	66	17.3
Pollution	108	28.3
Extinction of species	61	16.0
Total	382	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 4.17 presents the implications on the environment in the study area. The analysis of the findings shows that, the majority (147) of respondents in the urban cited increased waste accumulation especially in core centre of the Urban such as close to Sultan Palace, Bello Way and Moyijoroad that constitute 38.5 % of the respondents. This indicates that as population growth expand the volume of

waste generated also rise leading to challenge of waste management. However other major issue is "pollution which have serious implications human activity, air, water and land quality (28.3 %) and followed by Frequent flooding and erosion which are mostly rampant in areas of Tudunwada, Unguwar Makafi, Dallatu road and Gangaren Abu Kure which constitute 17.3%.This indicating population growth can disrupt natural drainage leading to heightened flood risk and soil erosion. Whereas other reveal the "Extinction of Species" such as plants and animals species especially in the sub -urban areas of the Urban which constitute 16.0 %., highlights the biodiversity loss that accompany urban expansion and habitat destruction. As natural areas are converted for residential, and commercial use, local wildlife may be threatened leading to ecological imbalance. The finding was also in line with Barrey and Haack 2006 rapid increase in human population in Urban areas affects modifications and structure and arrangement of urban centres globally, the tremendous pace of urban growth has resulted in multiple infrastructure and environmental challenges.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Based on the finding of the research obtained from both primary and secondary data on the impacts of population dynamics on growth and expansion of Sokoto Urban.

The finding reveals the socio demographic characteristics such as age, sex, education, income and occupation, the results revealed that 79 percent of the respondents are male while 21 percent are females which means the females respondents are few in the study. Based on the results it revealed 72.5 percent are married, 15.4 percent are single, widowed 8.6 percent and divorced consist only 3.4 percent. Therefore, socio demographic characteristics influenced population growth and urban expansion of the Urban.

The finding reveal the changes in population of Sokoto Urban over years which indicated population growth of city as witnessed from 1991 to 2024 population censuses and population projection data indicates population growth from 278,300- 740,512 residents which highlighted steady and consistent population growth over the years. The results also portray the major determinant of growth in the Urban birth rate due to form of marriage which accounted 58 percent, immigration 22.3 percent, the findings also reveal the major basic infrastructure in the Urban such as medical facilities 31.7 percent, pipe borne water 24.1 percent and road network 19.4 percent and also the land use pattern are mostly residential and commercial use. The finding was in line with Akintunde (2013) which stated that, Sokoto Urban was undergoing massive population growth due increased redistribution of activities and population changes and also expansion of built environment. Also Shamaki (2005) cited that population dynamics of Sokoto Urban changes its structure, size and composition over years and this was connected to growing of infrastructure such as health facilities, housing, business and road network

Furthermore, the finding reveal the physical growth and expansion of the Urban the results revealed significance urban expansion of the Urban of built up areas from 2000 to 2024 which indicated increased 138.40 percent more than double in size which indicating urbanization and development and also on the other hand the finding reveal significance decline of non-urban built landscape 28.40 percent which reflecting conversion land and vegetation to urban base uses and there also minor fluctuations of water bodies such as rivers which showed overall increased of 16.40 percent which slight increase of water bodies due to improved water management system. With this development Sokoto Urban witnessed growth and expansion coupled with formation of new areas such as Kalambaina housing estates, mana housing estates, old airport housing unit, Nasarawa Mana, Mana housing estates, Kwasai, Sabon Garin Tamaje, and Kwasai The finding suggest more provisions of social amenities to curtail the ever rising population such as Good road network, medical facilities and Schools. The finding was in line of Dankani2018 which stated that one of the challenges of urban growth is reduction of trees and vegetal cover across the cities. However the green cover was replaced with concrete slabs in most urban areas of the developed societies. Also Breimoh and Onishi stated that the urban in developing countries is diverse and alarming, as well the residential and industrial incursion of growing urban areas lead to constant decrease of high quality agricultural land and forest in the marginal areas of cities and in rural areas.

The finding reveal the implications of ever increasing population on selected basic infrastructure such as water, health, and housing. The finding revealed population pressure had negative impact on the rising population which resulted to over pressure of medical facilities 40.8 percent Such as

dispensaries, and medical personnel due to rising population and high risk of diseases 26.4 percent, pollution 18.0 and poor sanitary condition 13.9 percent. On the other hand the results revealed the impact of population available water sources majority of the respondents 58 percent and 28.3 cited contamination of water and pressure on the existing water sources are major problems of high population growth on available water sources. which needed to be addressed by government and private individuals. Finally, the finding also revealed the implications of rising population on the environment. Population growth had serious challenges on the environment especially accumulation of waste 38.5 percent which are prevalent in some areas of the Urban such as Ahmadu Bello, Gidadawa and Emir Yahaya and also pollution 38.5 percent from vehicular and industrial use. while flooding and soil erosion 17.3 in some areas of the Urban like Tudun Wada and Unguwar Makafi and the extinction of species such as vegetation and plants species. The finding was in line with Federal Government (2012) population increase exerting pressure on the environment, rapid deforestation resulting to unsustainable uses of forest resources for human survival e.g. fuel, wood, energy and housing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings and discussion of the research, the following conclusions are made. There was demographic changes in the structure and composition of study area over years which was connected to growing of infrastructure, economic activities and government policies. The major determinant of population dynamics was a birth rate and immigration rate especially in areas affected by banditry and also the level of economic activities in the study area contributed significantly in growth and expansion of the Urban. The study concluded that the core area or center of the urban are characterized with overcrowding, congestion and environmental pollution while the sub urban areas are characterized with wide space of land and local roads network. The research also shows the major problem or constraint in the study area ranging from congestion, waste disposal, lack of modern road network, lack of master of plans, shortage of electricity and shortage of water sources. Finally, population dynamics have impacted population growth, expansion and promote socio economic activities especially demands of land and commercial activities in the study area.

The following recommendation have been made based on the findings of the study:

- i. The government should adequate make provisions of basic Amenities in the newly formed areas such as water, electricity, good road network, hospital and telecommunication.
- ii. Government should conduct Population census timely rather than rely on projection to ensure equitable distribution of resources and income distribution among society.
- iii. There is need for urgent proactive planning for population dynamics with systematic use of available population data and the projection by Nigerian government, this will also enable development of technical capacity of technocrats and bureaucrat on programme design, research and implementation, in decision making for Sustainable Development processes.
- iv. The government and policy makers should adopt a cross sectorial and multidimensional approach to address the challenges of population, environmental change and sustainable development.
- v. The government and donor agencies should provide more funding and manpower to National population commission and other relevant agencies to carry out their responsibility properly and timely.
- vi. There also need to have proper data on birthrates, death rate, migration rate and health reproductive records in both government agencies and parastatals.
- vii. The Government needs to invest in human capital through people's education and sensitization to slow population growth through women empowerment and education.
- viii. There is need to have collaborate efforts from both government and individuals to combat insecurity in rural areas in order to reduce rural-urban migration in town and cities.
- ix. The civil society and non-governmental organization has to complement the effort of government in the citizens education on reproductive health, family planning, sustainable environmental management, poverty reduction.
- x. Government should implement measures to protect natural resources and develop effective waste management system to mitigate environmental impacts in the Urban

- xi. Policy makers should develop and implement policies that address population, urbanization and sustainable development.
- xii. Increase access to quality health care particularly for vulnerable population to address health challenges and reduce mortality and also investing in education infrastructure and program to equip growing population with necessary skills for economic development.
- xiii. Government should develop effective system of water supply and waste management to waterborne diseases and maintain public health.
- xiv. Government and individuals' organizations should foster economic growth by creating opportunities for entrepreneurship, jobs creation and investment

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